

The Mismatch Between Academia and the STI Industry: A Case Study of Uganda's Education System

Mwebaza Joy Gloria¹, David Musooli², Sylvia Sanyu Muge ma³, Brian Kathabasya⁴, Job Matovu⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Africa Renewal University – Buloba, Uganda.

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
20 February 2026

ABSTRACT

Uganda's pursuit of socio-economic transformation and industrialization continues to be hindered by a persistent mismatch between the skills produced by academic institutions and those required by the Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) sector. This study examines the causes, effects and potential solutions to this mismatch using secondary data from scholarly literature, government reports and policy documents. Findings reveal that rapid technological change, limited collaboration between universities and industry, low pass rates in science subjects, a STEM–Humanities imbalance and significant brain drain contribute to the widening skills gap. Evidence further shows that 55% of Uganda's workforce experiences education mismatch, with 11% over-educated and 44% under-educated for their roles. The mismatch negatively affects individual productivity and wages, reduces firm competitiveness and undermines national economic performance. The study proposes a systems-based approach, including curriculum co-design, industry-linked training, strengthened research funding and enhanced monitoring and evaluation mechanisms as pathways to realign academic programs with STI sector demands. Addressing this gap is essential for Uganda to advance technological innovation and achieve sustainable development goals.

Corresponding Author:
Mwebaza Joy Gloria

KEYWORDS: Science Technology Innovation sector, mismatch, academia

INTRODUCTION

The education system in Uganda is made up of primary, secondary and higher institutes of learning such tertiary institutes. Early primary education focused more on literacy and evolved into more theoretical subjects like social studies and science. Later on, more scientific subjects like biology, physics and history were given priority in high school. Uganda's tertiary level of education offers accreditation in degrees, diplomas and certificates in professional education and skills training. (Musa, 2024). The STI sector in Uganda is responsible for coordinating all activities and programs relating to research, science, technology and innovation. Due to various social and economic challenges in Uganda, the government, in 2007 approved the vision statement "A transformed Ugandan society from a peasant to a modern and prosperous country within 30 years". The government in conjunction with different stakeholders and government institutions developed a Uganda vision 2040 to make the vision statement operational. In recent years, five-year National Development Plans have been implemented (Onapa et al., 2020).

Currently, the fourth plan (NDPIV) is being executed. Despite the achievements registered from the implementation

of the previous plans, the use of and investment in STI is still low (0.14% of GDP in FY 2021/2022). The NDPIV highlights that there is a significant mismatch between the skills developed at formal institutions and the needs of the STI sector. It explains that this challenge has hindered Uganda's progress towards industrialization and socio-economic transformation. Educational programs, in most cases fail to align with the practical and technical demands of the STI sector, resulting in a workforce that lacks the specialized skills needed for research, innovation and technological advancement. They further attribute the skills gap to the low pass rates of science subjects at O-level (below 50%) which has reduced the enrolment rates in science related disciplines at higher levels of education. Additionally, the imbalance between STEM and Humanities graduates, currently at a ratio of 2:5 further widens the divide between education and STI industry needs. Moreover, the brain drain of skilled professionals to regions with stronger STI investment has further weakened the national talent pool. The rapid wave of digital transformation has created skills and jobs that are essential in developing new technologies and practically applying them (Da Fonseca, 2017). However, these emerging technological changes in the work place

demand specialized competencies that are not necessarily taught by educational institutes or fully developed in the labor market (Rikala et al., 2024). The mismatch also has far-reaching effects such as slow technological progress which leads to low innovation levels and research, low competitiveness in key economic sectors. (Republic of Uganda, 2024). Consequently, without a stronger alignment between education and the STI sector, Uganda risks falling behind in its pursuit of industrialization and sustainable economic growth. This necessitates interventions that can bridge between research institutions and the contexts in which knowledge is used, especially in developing countries (Leach & Scoones, 2006).

BACKGROUND

Uganda’s education, before the coming of missionaries, was primarily carried out in tribal groups. The education system was linked to survival and social life through dance, music and practical skills passed on throughout generations. With the coming of the missionaries, Uganda adopted western education which was more aligned to the European pattern (Scanlon et al., 1964). Despite the education reforms, Uganda has continued to face the challenge of graduate under-employment. Many higher education graduates, especially from technical and vocational training institutions, struggle to find roles that match their qualifications (Giz, 2022). Youth unemployment in Uganda stands between 64% and 70% with about 400,000 youths being released annually into the job market to compete for approximately 9,000 available jobs. As a result, nearly 30% of qualified graduates cannot find jobs with even fewer opportunities for semi-skilled and unskilled youths. (Magelah et al., 2014). The continuous unemployment struggles are partly driven by a mismatch between skills produced by the education system and those demanded by the labor market, leading to jobless growth and an underutilized workforce. (World Bank, 2023). Also, the private sector in Uganda notes that workers in the labor market across all sectors are inadequately prepared for employment, for example, the Uganda Manufacturers Association (UMA) reports that 68 percent of manufacturing firms faced difficulties hiring workers with the necessary technical skills, affecting productivity and growth (UMA, 2022).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The NDPV highlights that there is a significant mismatch between the skills developed at formal institutions and the needs of the STI sector in Uganda. Educational programs, in most cases fail to align with the practical and technical demands of the STI sector, resulting in a workforce that lacks the specialized skills needed for research, innovation and technological advancement (Republic of Uganda, 2024). Despite major education reforms, Uganda has continued to struggle with unemployment, especially among graduates. By the mid-2010s, graduate under-employment was already

evident with many higher education and vocational graduates unable to find jobs that matched their skills. Although technical institutions produce technicians and certificate holders, the labor market still has limited capacity to absorb them and the existing systems prevent their skills from translating into formal employment (Giz, 2022). Without a stronger alignment between education and the STI sector, Uganda risks falling behind in its pursuit of industrialization and sustainable economic growth (Leach & Scoones, 2006). This proposes interventions that can help to reduce this mismatch.

MAIN OBJECTIVE

To examine the causes, effects and possible solutions to the mismatch between academia and the STI sector in Uganda

SPECIFIC STUDY OBJECTIVES

To examine the causes of the mismatch between academia and the STI sector in Uganda.

To investigate the effects caused by the mismatch between academia and the STI sector in Uganda

To propose strategies that reduce the mismatch between academia and the STI sector in Uganda.

To examine the causes of the mismatch between academia and the STI sector in Uganda.

Morsy and Mukasa (2017) attribute this mismatch to several factors including rapid technological advancements, shifting job demands and disparities in education and training opportunities. Other scholars point out that in universities, training opportunities that meet industry demands remain insufficient particularly in software development where there’s a shortage of engineers who can write or customize software to meet specific industry needs. As for science and technology skills among Ugandan graduates, a number of industry representatives noted a lack of fundamental technical skills in areas like electronics repair and professional certifications required for specific capacities. The Science and Technology Sector Profile of Uganda notes that most research funding comes from external donors, whose priorities often shape research agendas. As a result, few research institutions focus on local challenges identified by domestic stakeholders, with much of the research concentrated primarily in health and agriculture (Brar et al., 2011). Moreover, the brain drain of skilled professionals to regions with stronger STI investment has weakened the national talent pool (Republic of Uganda, 2024). Other causes of mismatch are the growing emphasis on soft skills and misconceptions about industry skill requirements caused by a lack of cooperation and communication between education institutions and industries. (Rahman et al., 2024)

To investigate the effects caused by the mismatch between academia and the STI sector.

Morsy and Mukasa (2017) explain that the mismatches between academia and industry have far reaching

consequences at the individual, firm and macro levels. At the individual level, high levels of mismatch negatively affect the worker’s outcomes by lowering wages, reducing job satisfaction and increasing the chances of frequent job changes. At the firm level, the inability to find workers to perform required jobs has repercussions on the firm’s productivity, profitability, global competitiveness, growth and sometimes firm survival. Many African firms are forced to hire lower-skilled workers into positions that require higher competencies due to persistent skill shortages. At the macro level, structural skill deficits undermine national economic performance by reducing the country’s competitiveness and worsening unemployment.

To propose strategies that reduce the mismatch between academia and the STI sector in Uganda.

A systems approach should be employed because it recognizes the contribution of several actors in an interactive learning relationship and the factors that influence such a relationship (Ecuru, 2013). Applying this approach provides a useful pathway for reducing the mismatch between academia and industry in Uganda’s STI sector. Awareness of this need to consider factors beyond the educator led to the development of the social-ecological technology integration (SETI) framework which highlights the integration of technology within interconnected systems influenced by broader socio-economic factors (Crompton et al., 2023). The SETI organizational framework shows the distribution of responsibility for implementing a given policy in five distinct levels which are policy-planning, promotional level, performance level, science and technology services, evaluation level. For policy-planning (policy design), great emphasis should be placed on developing institutional mechanisms that incorporate the perspectives of the private sector and the needs of industry in curriculum development across all levels of education (Brar et al., 2011). Universities and industry stakeholders can jointly participate in curriculum design to ensure academic programs address current and emerging industry demands. Also, funding mechanisms should prioritize partnerships and projects that connect academic research with applied industry solutions. At the performance level, universities can focus on practical research, technological development and innovation that directly responds to industry challenges. Additionally, institutes can provide technical support and training to industry professionals while offering students hands-on experience. This highlights the need to extend training opportunities to technology users for example offering short courses to farmers (Brar et al., 2011). Lastly, continuous monitoring and evaluation is needed to ensure that academic programs and research outcomes meet industry standards and adapt to evolving STI needs. Coordinated collaboration among universities, research institutions and industry actors, supports sustainable growth in the country and the development of educational outputs that better align with labor market needs (Otim et al., n.d).

METHODOLOGY

This study entails a descriptive study of various literature sources that examine the mismatch between academia and the STI industry needs using secondary data. This secondary data was obtained from scholarly articles, policy documents, reports and other relevant publications that identified the causes, effects and possible solutions to the mismatch between academia and the STI sector needs in Uganda.

FINDINGS

The findings considered were based on results from a study where the determination of education mismatch was grounded in the ISCO-ISCED correspondence method that matches one’s education level attained with the appropriate occupation (Flisi et al., 2017). A study done found that 55% of Uganda’s workforce experiences an education mismatch. This mismatch indicated that out of the 55%, 11% of the workforce was over educated and 44% was under educated. The overeducated category meant that the workers possessed higher qualifications than what their jobs required while the under educated category meant that many workers lacked the skills or qualifications needed for their current roles (Namuliira et al., 2024).

Today, we see that Uganda is trying to strengthen its STI landscape through business research and development institutions such as the Uganda Industrial Research Institute which support industrialization by identifying and adapting affordable technologies that add value to local products so that they can be processed for national, regional and international markets. The institute provides technical assistance, knowledge, funding and partnerships for entrepreneurs seeking to enhance the technological and knowledge content of their products and processes. Additionally, Uganda has seen the growth of professional societies and conferences that foster communication, collaboration and networking among experts. Organizations such as the ICT Association of Uganda, Uganda Institution of Professional Engineers, Women Engineers, Technicians and Scientists, Uganda Broadcasting Council and the Uganda ISP Association provide valuable platforms for dialogue, professional support and capacity building within the STI ecosystem (Brar et al., 2011). Goulart et al. (2022) discovered that despite the fact that relevant graduates are employed in the IT industry, employees acquire the required job skills mainly through informal channels that the universities do not provide.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Uganda’s future labor market will demand a blend of technical, vocational and core skills to drive problem-solving and innovation across science, technology, engineering and mathematics related fields. These skills will enable workers to deploy, operate and maintain emerging technologies, giving them better employment prospects and greater mobility across jobs and sectors (Giz, 2022). Great emphasis

“The Mismatch Between Academia and the STI Industry: A Case Study of Uganda’s Education System”

should be placed on developing institutional mechanisms that incorporate the perspectives of the private sector and the needs of industry in curriculum development across all levels of education (Brar et al., 2011). With all actors in play, this mismatch will reduce significantly leading to sustainable growth of the country.

REFERENCES

1. Brar, S., Farley, S. E., Hawkins, R., Wagner, C. S., & The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank. (2011). *Science, Technology, and Innovation in Uganda*.
2. Crompton, H., Burke, D., Nickel, C., & Chigona, A. (n.d.). The SETI Framework and Technology Integration in the Digital Age. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 19(1), 2024. <http://www.asianjde.com/>
3. Da Fonseca, R. S. (2017). The Future of Employment: Evaluating the impact of STI foresight exercises. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-future-of-employment-evaluating-the-impact-of-sti-foresight-exercises>
4. Ecuru, J. 2013. Unlocking Potentials of Innovation Systems in Low Resource Settings. Karlskrona (Sweden), Blekinge Institute of Technology.
5. Flisi, S., Goglio, V. et al. (2017). Measuring Occupational Mismatch: Overeducation and Overskill in Europe—Evidence from PIAAC. *Social Indicators Research*, 131, 1211-1249. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-016-1292-7>
6. Giz. (2022). *EMPLOYMENT AND SKILLS STATUS REPORT (ESSR 2022)*.
7. Goulart VG, Liboni LB and Cezarino LO (2022) Balancing skills in the digital transformation era: the future of jobs and the role of higher education. *Industry and Higher Education* 36(2): 118–127. DOI: 10.1177/09504222211029796.
8. Magelah, P., Ntambirweki-Karugonjo, B., & Advocates Coalition for Development and Environment. (2014). Report of proceedings of the 49th session of the State of the Nation Platform. In *Infosheet: Vol. No. 26*. http://assets.fsnforum.fao.org.s3.amazonaws.com/public/discussions/contributions/infosheet_26.pdf
9. Ministry of Finance, Planning and Economic Development. (2021). Science, Technology and Innovations Sector: Semi-Annual Budget Monitoring Report - FY 2020/21. In *Ministry of Finance, Planning and Economic Development [Report]*. <https://archive.finance.go.ug/sites/default/files/Publications/STI%20Sector%20SemiAnnual%20Monitoring%20Report%20FY2020-21.pdf>
10. Morsy, H., & Mukasa, A. N. (2017). *Youth Jobs, Skill and Educational Mismatches in Africa*. <https://www.afdb.org/en/documents/publications/working-paper-series/>
11. Musa, K. J. (2024). Education in Uganda. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/657cd3ebee9e40a9b8e1c95t/668415663c10386c1283daa1/1719932266853/EDUCATION+IN+UGANDA.pdf>
12. Nakabugo M. G., Byamugisha A., & Bithaghalire J. (2008, April 30). *Future schooling in Uganda*. <https://hiroshima.repo.nii.ac.jp/records/2021431>
13. Namuliira, P., Kasiryee, I., Okillong, P., Atwine, B., Nakkazi, S. C., Nakitende, P., & Kajumba, M. M. (2024). *SKILLS ACQUISITION IN UGANDA: BRIDGING THE GAP BETWEEN EDUCATION AND EMPLOYMENT IN THE ERA OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION*. www.eprcug.org
14. Onapa, M. O., Sebbale, S., & Aguirre-Bastos, C. (2020). Harnessing science and technology knowledge for sustainability in Uganda.
15. Otim, M. O., Sebbale, S., & Aguirre-Bastos, C. (n.d.). Chapter 7. *Harnessing science and technology knowledge for sustainability in Uganda*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352573489>
16. Rahman, M. M., Alam, G. M., Aziz, N. a. B. A., Bashir, K., & Kader, R. (2024). Whether mismatch finds match in the digitalized era: A comparison of five types of graduates to align business education and banking jobs. *Industry and Higher Education*, 38(6), 547–561. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09504222241249900>
17. Republic of Uganda. (2024). Fourth National Development Plan (NDPIV) 2025/26 - 2029/30. In *republic of Uganda*. <https://parliamentwatch.ug/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/PDF-FINAL-NDPIV-for-Parliament-Approval-13122024-1.pdf>
18. Rikala, P., Braun, G., Järvinen, M., Stahre, J., & Hämäläinen, R. (2024). Understanding and measuring skill gaps in Industry 4.0 — A review. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 201, 123206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TECHFORE.2024.123206>
19. Scanlon, D., Teachers College, Columbia University, Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, U.S., Bureau of International Education, & Division of International Studies and Services. (1964). *Education in Uganda* (Report No. 32). Office of Education. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED544160.pdf>
20. The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank. <https://digitalregulation.org/wp-content/uploads/Science-Technology-and-Innovation-in-Uganda.pdf>
21. Tilak Naik, G. & Vaikunth Pai T. (2018). A Study on Products and Services of Apple Inc. International

Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE), 2(2), 67-76.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1491388>.

22. World-Bank. (2023). Delivering Growth to People through Better Jobs. Africa’s Pulse, No. 28, October 2023.
<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/40388>

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL NOTES

1. Mwebaza Joy Gloria holds a bachelor’s degree in Computer Engineering from Makerere University. She is currently pursuing a masters in Organizational Leadership at Africa Renewal University.
2. Dr. David Musooli holds a PhD in leadership studies and a Masters of Arts in Contextualized Pastoral Ministry from Lancaster Bible College PA, USA, and a bachelor’s of Science in Agriculture from Makerere University.
3. Mrs. Sylvia Sanyu Mugema holds a bachelor’s of Commerce and a Master’s of Science in Accounting and Finance from Makerere University. She is currently the director finance and pursuing doctoral studies.
4. Mr. Brian Kathabasya holds a bachelor’s degree in Information Technology from Uganda Pentecostal University -UPU and a Post graduate Diploma from Uganda Management Institute. He is currently the assistant academic registrar at Africa Renewal University.
5. Dr. Job Matovu holds a PhD in Information Technology from Makerere University, graduated with a Masters in Information Technology and a Bachelors in Business Computing from Uganda Christian University-Mukono. He is a leading researcher in Payment Information Technologies Security with a bias on Authentication. He is a Researcher and Lecturer in the Department of Information Technology at Africa Renewal University. His research interests include: Cyber Security, Electronic Commerce, Business Information Systems, ICT policy and strategy, ICT4D, mobile and wireless technologies, artificial intelligence and database management systems among others.